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Educational Inequality in Italy: A Capability Approach¹

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Abstract

The aim of the paper is to investigate Italian inequality in education by applying Amartya Sen's capability approach to the data derived from a survey carried out by the Italian Statistical Institute, entitled "Aspect of Daily Life". This is the first-ever use of the survey for this kind of analysis which refers to the period 1993-2012.

Educational inequalities (in our case, especially at a local level) represent an essential dimension of inequality *tout court*. In the econometric section, we will use the Oaxaca Blinder decomposition technique to investigate the causes of the educational Gap between the South and Centre-North of Italy in terms of differences of public and private resources allocations, and their different outcome in terms of educational achievements. Then, by applying the GMM model, a dynamic panel analysis will be conducted to evaluate the factors influencing individual educational inequality and to test for the existence of an educational Kuznets Curve integrated to the level of public resources in education and to economic wealth inequality. The results will prove that the Southern Gap is significant and depending on the difference of the levels. As to the efficacy of public resources allocation in

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education, public expenditure in Centre-North appears to be more effective even if this area receives less funds than the South. Moreover, the dynamic panel analysis will show that an Educational Kuznets Curve exists, that economic inequality has a strong impact and public expenditure is a valid instrument for educational equity.

JEL codes: I24, I25, I28, C51

Keywords: Education, Inequality, Capabilities, pseudo-panel, dynamic panel model

1. Introduction

Education is a central factor for social and economic progress and many studies have highlighted various aspects that make education a bridge between economic systems and society (Vladimirova and Le Blanc, 2015; Rambla and Langthaler 2016; UNESCO 2017) In theoretical and empirical growth literature, education is mainly understood as human capital, which, with labour and physical capital, permits to increase income. In growth literature, since the pioneering work of Lucas's work (1986), human capital has been studied as an engine of economic development, while in microeconomic literature, since Becker's research (1964) and Mincer's study (1974) the human capital investment function has been studied and estimated to capture economic returns. The European Union bases its policies on the advancements on education as an instrument of social inclusion as well as an engine of economic competitiveness. The previous Lisbon strategy and the current Europe 2020 strategy for the period 2014-2020 attest the European efforts to promote educational development to relaunch economy and accelerate a process of smart and inclusive growth.

We will focus on inequality in education, which is examined mainly by applying the capability approach of Amartya Sen. Specifically, the main aim of this paper is to investigate inequality in education among individuals and between geographic areas in Italy by using for the first time the data obtained from the "Aspect of Daily Life" (ADL) survey. This survey has been carried out annually by the Italian Statistical Institute (ISTAT) since 1993. The Italian case is interesting because the social and economic disparity between the Centre-North and disadvantaged South and Islands (henceforth South) implies that Italian Regions attain the highest (such as Lombardy) and the lowest positions (such as Calabria) in the European regional rankings of economic and social development disparities. After having illustrated the features of this approach, the paper focuses on the relevance

of educational inequality in theoretical and empirical terms. The empirical analysis of the paper is the following: firstly, the factors influencing the educational Gap at regional level will be investigated through the Oaxaca-Blinder decomposition; secondly, a GMM panel model will be applied to evaluate the variables that affect individual educational inequality by extending the Educational Kuznets Curve model through the inclusion of public and private resources variables. The results show that the Southern Gap is significant and depending on the difference of the levels. As to the allocation of public resources in education, even if the South receives higher funds, public investments in central and northern Italy are more effective. We find evidence of an inverted-U Kuznets curve describing the relationship between levels of education and inequality. Moreover, economic inequality has a strong influence on education attainment and inequality while public expenditure seems to be a valid instrument to pursue educational equity.

The original use of a longitudinal database and the territorial perspective of the capability approach analysis are the strengths of the paper. Indeed, most of the studies on this topic use cross-sectional data to analyse a phenomenon that is essentially longitudinal, thus requiring a panel or longitudinal survey data to analyse the relationship between the educational level and the resources used in education while controlling individual heterogeneity. In addition, cross-sectional data are not adequate to test Kuznets's hypothesis (Deininger and Squire, 1998, Meschi and Scervini, 2013). However, due to the high costs and the methodological issues that reduce the information obtained from panel samples, this type of statistical data is seldom available. On the other hand, cross-section social surveys are widely carried out on a regular basis resulting in an available series of independent cross-sectional data. In this paper, we use a unique data set we created by combining micro-data for the period 1993-2012, obtained from 19 waves of the ISTAT ADL survey. These data permit to compute measures of educational attainment and educational inequality by taking into account various geographical areas and different level of aggregation.

We referred to additional sources of data in order to include variables related to the territorial areas in which individuals live (such as geographical dummies variables) and information regarding public expenditure on education. In this way, we examined the role of public and private resources in accumulation of education and in educational inequality.

The remaining sections of the paper are structured as follows. Section 2 reviews the theoretical and empirical contributions useful to better understand the research question; section 3 illustrates the research goals and specifies the econometric models; Section 4 describes the data and reports descriptive statistics; section 5 presents the main results of our empirical analysis. Finally, section 5 contains the conclusions.

2. Background Literature

In the capability approach, human life is a set of beings and doings. Well-being is conceived as the beings and doings that individuals “value and have reason to value” (Sen, 1999 p.18), e.g. being educated, being healthy, resting, working, and is the output of a process starting from resources. Individuals can convert resources (goods and/or services, public and/or private) in capabilities which are the type of resources that enable agents to do and to be. People can choose to realise these real opportunities by transforming them in achieved functionings. Thus, well-being is a set of capabilities and in this perspective “development is freedom” (Sen, 1999). Conversion factors are everything that fosters the conversion of resources in capabilities and are personal (e.g. metabolism, physical condition, sex, reading skills, intelligence), social (e.g. public policies, social norms, discriminating practises, gender roles, societal hierarchies, power relations) and environmental factors (e.g. climate, geographical location) (Robeyns, 2005, p.99).

In a well-being process, education has an intrinsic value and an instrumental value. As an end (in itself), education is a human capability, “the ability of human beings to lead lives they have reason to value and to enhance the substantive choices they have” (Sen, 1997 p.1959), or is intended as “being able to be educated and to use and produce knowledge” (Robeyns, 2003). Thus, education is one of the basic capabilities. Indeed, at a macro level, Education is one of the dimensions of the Human Development Index, with Income and Health (UNDP, 2017).

As a tool, education can enlarge human capabilities by assuming two kinds of roles: an instrumental social role, by enabling people to participate in the public debate and by empowering social categories that are disadvantaged, and an instrumental process role by facilitating people in decision-making at a micro or macro level (Sen, 1992). Moreover, in the labour market, skills and competences can represent resources for the capability “to be able to work or to undertake projects” (Robeyns, 2003). In other ways, interactions across capabilities are frequent and relevant and depending on the type of capability that can have a role of resource or of conversion factor for other capability. For instance, empirical studies have highlighted that education can be an important conversion factor of the capability “to have good health, including reproductive health” (Nussbaum, 2003). Finally, Sen, agreeing with mainstream economic literature, recognizes the importance of education as human capital, as a productive factor and as a boost to economic growth. This is not the focus of his study, but Sen considers the two perspectives complementary, due to the multivalent nature of education in economic development and social development (Sen, 1997).

Inequality is a main topic of the capability approach, according to which individuals and groups diverge in the well-being process for their abilities to convert resources in capabilities.

Educational inequality is one of the most analysed forms of inequality because education is a relevant capability for inclusion in a social and economic system (Robeyns, 2006; Terzi, 2008). Inequality in education has both intrinsic and instrumental value. As an end, inequality in education concerns equity and social justice and is a basic capability because its moral dimension is universally recognised (Norheim, and Asada. 2009). The two major forms of inequality analysed are in previous studies: vertical inequality across people and horizontal inequality across social groups (Stewart, 2005). Overall, inequality in education influences educational levels negatively (Mayer 2000, 2001; Haveman and Smeeding 2006), and many studies show that inequality in education favours inequality in income (Reheme, 2007) and also curbs the economic growth, (see, among many, García-Penalosa, 1994, Aghion *et al.* 1999, Sauer and Zagler, 2014, Galor 2009) by causing, for example, political instability and credit market imperfections (Castelló-Climent, 2010). Finally, inequality in education has a spillover effect on labour conditions, social exclusion, demographic dynamic, governance (Melamed and Samman, 2013).

The analysis of inequality concerns disadvantaged categories of individuals such as females, ethnic minorities, children with disabilities (Denuelin and Shahani, 2009). In this article, we study inequality in education from both an individual and a territorial perspective. As to individual inequality outside the capability approach, some studies estimate the Educational Kuznets Curve, namely an inverted U curve which relates education level and educational inequality. According to De Gregorio and Lee (2002) and Londono (1996)², the parabolic relation between educational inequality and educational levels depends on the fact that at low levels of education, the increase of education provokes inequality, while when the majority of people have a secondary school diploma and only few students attend university courses, the increase in the number of tertiary students reduces inequality. However, results in this type of studies vary: some scholars confirm this functional form, such as Ram (1990), Park (1996), Londono (1996) Thomas *et al.* (2001), and De Gregorio and Lee (2002) Morrison and Martin (2012), while others, such as Castellò and Domenech (2002) and Meschi and Scervini (2014), find out an inverse educational Kuznets Curve. We will contribute to this debate by verifying the existence of an educational Kuznets curve in a function with public and private resources in Italy for the period 1993-2012.

According to the capability approach, territory can influence educational attainment and inequality in education as an environmental conversion factor. Moreover, aggregated analyses take

² “In a society where nobody has access to education, the level of education is zero and the variance of education among the population is naturally zero. In a society where the entire population reaches the maximum level of education, the level of education is at the maximum, but the variance, again, is zero [...] In the interim period, the variance of education tends to rise with the increase in the level of education until it reaches a turning point, after which it decreases” (Londono, 1996 p.13).

into account the so called *collective capabilities*, which can be defined as the averages of the individual capabilities or as the capabilities that can be achieved only collectively (Evans 2002; Stewart 2005; Ibrahim 2006; Ballet, Dubois, Mahieu 2007). Biggeri and Ferrannini (2016) develop a framework where individual and collective capabilities strongly interact and territory assumes a relevant role not as “the container” but as a “driver” of cultural, social and institutional local energies. A study of the Bank of Italy (Bertola and Sestito, 2011) on education in Italy from 1860 (Italian unification) to the present illustrates that education as human capital has been relevant for the Italian economic development; since the second half of the 1990s, the slowdown of the Italian economy has been strongly linked with a worsening of the Italian educational system. The Educational Gap between the North and the South has characterised Italy since its origins: it consists both in quantitative differences (such as illiteracy rates, school years) and qualitative differences (as revealed by recent international surveys on students competences, such as OECD’s PISA).

This paper originally contributes to this debate by verifying the role of public and private resources in educational accumulation and inequality. By using 19 waves of the ISTAT ADL survey, we apply a pseudo panel approach (Verbeek, 2008) that allows the construction of an original database which combines temporal (from 1993 to 2012), geographical (19 regions) and individual dimensions (more than 840,000 individuals). Moreover, the territorial perspective is also considered by applying the Oaxaca-Blinder decomposition method. The following section focuses on an econometric analysis of the Southern Educational Gap and of educational inequality across individuals.

3. Econometric models

3.1 Southern Educational Gap

In order to describe the above mentioned well-being process suggested by Sen (1985, 1986), various empirical studies (such as Chiappero Martinetti, 2008; Kuklys, 2005) have estimated the following “conversion function” equation:

$$(1) \quad Y_i = \mathbf{x}'_i \boldsymbol{\beta} + \mathbf{z}'_i \boldsymbol{\gamma}$$

where Y_i is the educational achieved functioning, \mathbf{x}'_i indicates resources and \mathbf{z}'_i conversion factors, while $\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\gamma} > 0$ are the vectors of parameters indicating the conversion ratios. With the aim of analysing the Educational Gap between the North and the South we refer to model (1) and define the following expression:

$$(2) \quad \Delta Y = Y_{CN} - Y_S$$

where Y_{CN}, Y_S are the years of schooling in the Centre-North and in the South of Italy, respectively. According to the Oaxaca-Blinder model (Blinder 1973; Oaxaca 1973; Jann 2008), we will decompose equation (2) in the following way:

$$(3) \Delta Y = \{\beta_S \Delta X + \gamma_S \Delta Z\} + \{\Delta \beta X_S + \Delta \gamma Z_S\} + \{[\beta_S \Delta X \Delta \beta X] + [\gamma \Delta Z \gamma Z_S]\}$$

According to equation (3) the Educational Gap between the North and the South of Italy is composed of three terms: the endowments effect, $\{\beta \Delta X + \gamma \Delta Z\}$, concerning the difference in the levels of regressors; the coefficients effect $\{\Delta \beta X_S + \Delta \gamma Z\}$, which is essentially the difference in the coefficients of regressors and the interaction effect $\{[\beta_S \Delta X \Delta \beta X] + [\gamma \Delta Z \gamma Z_S]\}$, which is the product of two previous terms. Therefore, the gap can depend on the difference in the level of resources and/or the conversion rate of the resources. In other words, we have tried to answer the following questions: Does the Gap between the northern and southern regions depend on the relative scarcity of resources or rather on the relative ineffectiveness in the use of resources. Since the two aspects are integrated, in order to highlight the resource effect, the method assumes that the two macro-areas considered have the same coefficient β_S, γ_S ; in order to identify the effect of the conversion rates it assumes that they have the same level for each variable X_S, Z_S .

The decomposition is obtained by combining the versions of the following equation for the data of the Centre-North and the South:

$$(4) EDU_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 PRIV_{it-1} + \beta_2 PUB_{it-1} + \beta_3 (PRIV_{it-1} * PUB_{it-1}) + \gamma_1 WOM_{it-1}$$

EDU is the outcome variable expressed by the educational level. We considered as resources PUB and $PRIV$, indicating respectively public expenditure in education (per person) and an index of private economic wealth. Equation (4) is composed of individual and environmental conversion factors, represented by variable WOM , which expresses the percentage of women in the Italian population, and regional dummies. The method of estimation is the Oaxaca-Blinder decomposition through pooled OLS, with regional dummies, robust errors and taking into account the time trend. All variables are expressed in logarithms and time lags are introduced to avoid endogeneity problems linked with simultaneity. We also estimated the pooled model. Therefore, the decomposition equation is expressed as:

$$(5) \Delta EDU_{it} = \beta_{1S} \Delta PRIV_{it-1} + \beta_{2S} \Delta PUB_{it-1} + \beta_{3S} \Delta (PRIV_{it-1} * PUB_{it-1}) + \gamma_{1S} \Delta WOM_{it-1} + \Delta \beta_1 PRIV_{St-1} + \Delta \beta_2 PUB_{St-1} + \Delta \beta_3 (PRIV_{St-1} * PUB_{St-1}) + \Delta \gamma_1 \Delta WOM_{it-1}$$

3.2 Individual Educational Inequality

In order to analyze the factors influencing the educational inequality and verify the Educational Kuznets Curve , we estimated the following equation:

$$(6) I_{EDU_{it}} = \delta_0 + \delta_1 I_{EDU_{it-1}} + \delta_2 I_{PRIV_{it}} + \delta_3 I_{PRIV_{it}}^2 + \delta_4 PUB_{it} + \delta_5 PUB_{it}^2 + \delta_6 EDU_{it} + \delta_7 EDU_{it}^2$$

The variable I_{EDU} expresses the degree of educational inequality, while I_{PRIV} measures the inequality of individuals' wealth. The econometric method used is the dynamic panel GMM model, considering the one step and two step versions, useful to take into account potential endogeneity due to the simultaneity among the variables. Variables EDU_{it} and EDU_{it}^2 are introduced in order to verify the so called Educational Kuznets Curve. It is worth noting that all variables are expressed in logarithms and time trend is considered.

As mentioned in the introduction, we used a pseudo-panel approach, that has become more and more popular over the last few years and is applied in various fields to conduct a range of analyses of the relationship between experience–earnings profiles and education (Brunello and Comi, 2004), of cognitive achievement dynamics (De Simone 2013) and poverty (Dang et al 2014). However, to the authors' best knowledge, so far few studies have applied pseudo-panel techniques to the analysis of educational inequality (an exception is represented by Meschi and Scervini, 2013).

Although repeated cross section data cannot follow the same individuals over time, there are certain advantages in using them rather than genuine panel data. Indeed, like all sample surveys, longitudinal surveys are affected by non-random attrition and the non-response in panel surveys tends to accumulate over time as further waves of interviewing are conducted (Watson and Wooden 2009).

As to the choice of the estimation method, it is worth noting that when dynamic panel data are constructed from repeated cross-sections, the individuals for which the group mean of lagged dependent variables is computed are different from those for which the group mean of dependent variables is computed (Inoue 2008). Moffitt (1993) extends Deaton's (1985) approach to the estimation of a dynamic model based on independent cross-sections by proposing a two-stage least squares estimator to address this issue. Moffitt (1993) interpreted the within estimator as an instrumental variables estimator, with cohort dummy variables which fulfil the role of instruments, by suggesting to replace the lagged dependent variable by its predicted value, obtained from data available at time t-1. However, Moffitt's (1993) estimator is inconsistent when time-varying exogenous regressors are used (Verbeek and Vella, 2005). Girma (2000) proposes a quasi-differencing approach that takes quasi-difference of the dependent variables of two individuals in the same group and uses explanatory variables of a third individual in the group as instruments. Using

time-invariant instruments, Verbeek and Vella (2005) propose an augmented instrumental variables (IV) approach unifying the existing estimators for dynamic pseudo-panel data models, and present identification conditions underlying these estimators. Collado (1997) applies the Arellano and Bond (1991) instruments for genuine panel data to the pseudo-panel case with homogenous parameters, obtaining a measurement-error corrected GMM estimator that is consistent as the number of cohorts, $C \rightarrow \infty$, for fixed T and fixed n_g .

In related work, McKenzie (2004) considers the FE and Arellano-Bond type IV estimators thus allowing for heterogeneous parameters across groups where the number of individuals and the number of groups can be both large.

In this paper, we also use an Arellano-Bond type IV estimator and we consider as endogenous variables the level of wealth and education (Blundell and Bond, 1998). The Hansen J test provided us with empirical support of the validity of the selected instruments.

4. Data and model specification

Our analysis relies on a data set we created combining micro-data from 19 waves of the Italian multipurpose ADL survey. Indeed, in May 2014 the Italian Statistical Institute released micro-data from this wide multipurpose survey, thus providing us with a rich dataset on various social aspects including detailed information on individual educational achievement, expressed as the highest qualification achieved, work, family and social life, spare time, political and social participation health and life style. Each year the ADL survey, as part of an integrated system of social surveys, involves a random sample of about 50,000 individuals (20,000 households) distributed in 19 Italian regions (Piedmont and Valle d'Aosta are considered as only one region).

We have limited our analyses to individuals aged 18 and over at the time of the survey. This selection has produced annual sample sizes ranging from 40,000 to 50,000 individuals, leading us to a pooled dataset consisting of 848,634 individuals.

With the aim of analysing the role of the educational levels, we have computed for each individual the numbers of years of education completed. The variable ranges from 0 – for those individuals who did not even complete one year of education – and 20 for individuals who completed the tertiary level of education (master or doctoral level).

In order to measure individuals' private economic wealth (variable PRIV in equation 4), we constructed a composite relative indicator through the Multiple Correspondence Analysis (MCA). Indeed, MCA has been employed for the construction of composite indicators when only categorical

variables are available. Similarly, Principal Component Analysis is used for constructing composite indicators when only quantitative variables are available. The general formulation and the steps we carried out to construct the Composite Wealth Indicator (CWI) can be summarized as follows. From our data set we firstly identified five variables as proxies of individuals' wealth status, available in the ADL survey, to be included in the MCA: i) dwelling ownership; ii) whether one has spent a holiday period of at least 4 nights in the last 12 months or not; iii) number of cars owned; iv) judgment concerning the economic resources of all household members (categories ranging from "excellent" to "totally inadequate"). Then, we computed the CWI by using the weights obtained from the MCA as the ratio between the factor score s on the first axis normalized by the eigenvalue. Therefore, the CWI can be expressed as

$$CWI = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{j_k}^{J_k} W_{j_k}^k I_{j_k}^k$$

where k is the number of dimensions (variables) with $k=(1,2,\dots,K=5)$, j the number of modalities of each dimension with $j=(1,2,\dots,J)$ and I the binary (0/1) indicator of each modality. According to the above expression, the composite indicator can be viewed as the average across dimensions (variables) of the weighted sum of each binary modality of each dimension. Lastly, we referred to the min-max approach to obtain the relative CWI ranging between 0 and 1.

In order to measure the degree of inequality in educational level and private resources, we employed the Gini index, which has been increasingly used by several authors to assess education inequality (Meschi and Scervini, 2013; Checchi, 2001; Thomas et al., 2001), even though earlier studies computed it by using attainment level from Barro and Lee (2001). The Gini index is the most widely employed in the literature of economic inequality because of its convenient features: it is scale-invariant; it is bounded between zero and one, and can also be defined for values zero of the relevant variable. Thus, we could also include individuals with no formal education.

Since we measured educational levels by using years of schooling, derived from individual answers we could treat them as a continuous variable and compute the Gini index expressed by

$$G_x = \frac{1}{2\mu} \sum_i \sum_j \frac{|x_i - x_j|}{N^2}, \forall i, j \in N.$$

After having calculating these variables for all the individuals in our pooled dataset, we referred to the pseudo-panel approach according to which individuals sharing some common characteristics (i.e. year of birth) are grouped into cohorts. The averages within these cohorts were then treated as observations in a pseudo-panel data set. From a statistical methodological perspective,

this is equivalent to an instrumental variable approach where the grouping indicators are used as instruments (Verbeek, 2008).

When constructing a pseudo panel, there is a trade-off between the need to have a large number of observations per cohort and the desire to have as much informative data as possible. On the one hand, a larger number of cohorts and, hence, of data points increases the heterogeneity of the pseudo-panel by increasing the variations between groups; on the other, it decreases the average number of individuals per cohort resulting in less precise estimates of the cohort means (Baltagi 2005). As shown by Verbeek and Nijman (1992), measurement error becomes negligible when cohort sizes are large (at least over 100 individuals) and the time variation in the cohort means is sufficiently large.

In order to ensure that the cohort means of the variables based on the sample are reasonable estimates of the population cohort variables, we based the construction of the pseudo-panel ~~is based~~ on the year of birth and the region in which the respondents reside.

Since, as already mentioned, we focused on individuals aged 18 or over, and considered 19 repeated cross-sections, we defined 9 age cohorts (1921-1926, 1927-1932, 1933-1938, 1939-1944, 1945-1950, 1951-1956, 1957-1962, 1963-1968, 1969-1975) and considered the Italian regions included in the ISTAT survey³. Thus, by crossing years of birth and regions we obtained 171 groups, which have generated 3249 observations ($i=1\dots, 171$; $t=1\dots, 19$; $n=3249$) in 19 years. In this way, we constructed a series of means of the variables included in the data set and inserted them in our models by considering the individuals belonging to the same birth cohort from 1993 to 2012.

5. Results

5.1 The evolution of educational attainment and educational inequality

Figure 1 shows the trend of years of schooling (variable *EDU*) in Italy in the period 1993-2012. The dynamic of this variable is changing in Italy, almost doubling the initial level by achieving 10 years on average. The South of Italy has a relative disadvantage and the gap with the Centre-North decreases from 1993 to 1997, while in the following period is constant and stands at about 1 year of education. It is worth noting that the economic crisis appears to have exacerbated the distance between the North and the South in terms of educational levels.

³ It is worth noting that in the ADL survey 19 regions are considered: Piemonte and Valle d'Aosta as a single region; Lombardia; Veneto; Trentino Alto Adige; Friuli Venezia Giulia; Emilia Romagna; Liguria; Toscana; Marche; Lazio; Umbria; Abruzzo; Campania; Basilicata; Molise; Calabria; Puglia; Sicilia; Sardegna.

Figure 2 reports Gini indices of the years of education for the period 1993-2012 by considering the two Italian macro-areas.

Despite the overall reduction of educational inequality, the dispersion of educational attainment still varies between the Centre-North and the South, with the first regions showing higher levels of inequality in educational levels over the period under examination. These differences may be due to heterogeneous use of resources and educational policies.

Figure 1 The Educational Gap between the South and the Centre-North of Italy, 1993-2012.

Figure 2 The Evolution of the Educational Gini Index in the South and Centre-North of Italy, 1993-2012

Figures 1 and 2 underline the expansion of educational attainment that occurred over the studied period and the contemporaneous decrease in educational inequality with an exception for the South of Italy in 2011-2012.

Table 1 presents summary statistics of years of schooling and Gini coefficient for educational attainment for each Italian region at five-year intervals from 1993 to 2012. On average, since 1993 educational attainment has increased throughout the regions even if with different growth rates. For most of the Italian regions, such as Piemonte, Lombardia and Molise, educational inequality has first increased and then decreased, while in Campania inequality seems to worsen during the period 1993-2012.

In 2012, the highest levels of Gini were in Piemonte-Valle d'Aosta for the Centre-North and Campania for the South, while the least "inequal" Regions in education were Lazio and Sicilia, (see Table 1).

Table 1- Summary statistics: average values by Italian regions

Italian Regions	Average Year of Education Cross-sections					Gini Education Cross-sections				
	1993	1998	2003	2008	2012	1993	1998	2003	2008	2012
Piemonte	8.711	8.823	9.210	9.641	10.140	0.250	0.259	0.266	0.312	0.298
Lombardia	8.816	9.304	9.634	10.191	10.214	0.250	0.260	0.272	0.304	0.285
Trentino-Alto Adige	8.521	9.117	9.488	10.048	10.327	0.248	0.268	0.258	0.298	0.286
Veneto	8.158	8.889	9.323	9.524	10.114	0.243	0.259	0.263	0.301	0.285
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	8.728	9.544	9.601	9.910	10.281	0.248	0.251	0.266	0.290	0.278
Liguria	8.690	9.426	9.722	9.737	10.574	0.247	0.249	0.252	0.287	0.279
Emilia-Romagna	8.213	8.878	9.213	9.637	10.276	0.247	0.264	0.254	0.303	0.274
Toscana	8.227	8.576	9.207	9.471	10.097	0.247	0.238	0.259	0.309	0.273
Umbria	8.254	8.561	9.283	9.928	10.402	0.250	0.250	0.245	0.284	0.285
Marche	8.109	8.303	8.995	9.503	9.977	0.241	0.243	0.245	0.292	0.275
Lazio	8.984	9.505	9.877	10.699	11.045	0.238	0.249	0.244	0.288	0.271
Abruzzo	8.144	8.623	9.305	9.581	10.120	0.239	0.246	0.247	0.288	0.271
Molise	7.831	7.819	8.592	9.643	9.614	0.237	0.231	0.236	0.295	0.281
Campania	8.543	8.965	9.432	9.493	9.734	0.247	0.247	0.244	0.286	0.296
Puglia	8.210	8.245	8.821	9.024	9.188	0.242	0.238	0.239	0.284	0.269
Basilicata	7.531	8.180	8.695	9.109	9.257	0.236	0.236	0.234	0.284	0.270
Calabria	8.309	8.229	8.711	9.302	9.914	0.233	0.221	0.224	0.284	0.268
Sicilia	8.261	8.308	8.695	9.223	9.487	0.236	0.227	0.222	0.270	0.248
Sardegna	7.932	8.482	8.726	9.190	9.618	0.234	0.237	0.220	0.287	0.266
Italy	8.385	8.861	9.286	9.704	10.074	0.289	0.274	0.265	0.261	0.251

Figure 3 shows the nonlinearity in the relationship between educational attainment and educational inequality, although with different dynamics over time. More specifically, in most of the Italian regions, educational levels become more unequal with a higher average number of completed years of schooling, which may rise to 9-10, and then they start to level off.

Figure 3 Average Years of Education vs. Education Gini Coefficient by Italian Regions, 1993-2012

5.2 Econometric analysis

Table 2 shows all estimates concerning the analysis of the educational Gap between the South and Centre-North of Italy obtained by using OLS models separately for Centre-North, South and Italy. These estimations are the starting points for the Oaxaca-Blinder Decomposition, which calculates the endowments and coefficients effects. OLS regressions show that all resources are useful for educational achievements, and that private resources are more effective than public resources to increase the years of schooling; indeed, in all regressions the coefficients of the former are about ten times higher than those of the latter. The coefficient of the interaction variable PRIV*PUBL is positive, indicating that public and private resources are complementary for educational improvements. This confirms various international empirical studies (such as Jacobs and van der Ploeg, 2005), according to which public expenditure stimulates household expenditure for education mainly for primary and secondary schools. Gender educational inequality is significant principally in the South of Italy; indeed, the coefficients of variable WOM are all negatives. In particular, the coefficient for the South of Italy is twice as strong as the one in the Centre-North. This result confirms gender inequality in education. This is a serious problem because education represents a valid instrument for women empowerment both in developing and in developed countries or areas, such as

the South of Italy (Medel-Anonuevo, 1995). Finally, regional dummies are significant, showing the relevance of the “environmental factors” within the educational conversion process.

The Oaxaca-Blinder decomposition method attains the following relevant and diversified results. The Educational Gap between the South and Centre-North of Italy is significant and depends not only on the endowment effect but also on the coefficient effect. As to the allocation of private resources, the Centre-North of Italy obtains more economic endowment, but the South expends it more effectively: indeed, the difference between the coefficients is negative, because the southern coefficient is higher than the centre- northern one. Namely, given the same level of wealth, the educational returns of the South are higher than those of Centre-North. For what concerns public expenditure per capita in education, the educational Gap between the South and Centre-North of Italy seems to depend not on the scarcity but rather on the quality of public fund allocation and use. Namely, the endowment difference is negative (in favour of the South), while the coefficient difference is positive (in favour of the Centre-North).

Table 2 Estimation Results on the Southern Educational Gap.

	OLS Models			Oaxaca-Blinder Decomposition				
	<i>CENTRE-NORTH</i>	<i>SOUTH</i>	<i>ITALY</i>	Gap decomposition		Decomposition Regressions		
				CENTRE-NORTH		SOUTHERN GAP		
						<i>Endowments</i>	<i>Coefficients</i>	
PRIV	5.352*** (0.173)	4.000*** (0.345)	4.659*** (0.178)	SOUTH	2.135*** (0.005)	PRIV	0.269*** (0.007)	-0.598*** (0.001)
PUB	0.333*** (0.090)	0.504** (0.227)	0.412*** (0.099)	SOUTHERN GAP	1.991*** (0.006)	PUB	-0.106*** (0.003)	0.019*** (0.001)
PUB_PRIV	0.601*** (0.207)	0.934** (0.448)	0.728*** (0.215)	ENDOWMENTS EFFECT	0.143*** (0.008)	PUB_PRIV	0.078*** (0.002)	-0.009*** (0.001)
WOM	-0.930*** (0.060)	-1.800*** (0.122)	-1.333*** (0.063)	COEFFICIENTS EFFECT	0.101*** (0.008)	WOM	-0,002 (0.004)	-0.561*** (0.001)
Observations	1,683	1,224	2,907					
R2	0.5668	0.2967	0.4183					
F test	138.55***	40.69***	88.07***					

The second part of the empirical analysis is focused on the identification of the factors influencing educational inequality in Italy (Roodman, 2009). The presence of an Educational Kuznets Curve for Italy in the period 1993-2012 was tested by using the Dynamic panel-data method. From Table 3 interesting results emerge. Firstly, individual inequality in education is path dependent: the coefficient of the lagged Educational Gini Index is positive. This result signals a divergent social

process that precludes social mobility. It weakens the relationship between social progress and economic development (Guarini et al., 2016).

Secondly, there seems to be a strong link between economic and educational inequality: the coefficient of inequality of individuals' wealth (I_{PRIV}) is significant and positive. Moreover, this link is exponential: the coefficient of the square of individuals' wealth is positive and statically significant. This result illustrates a socioeconomic trap: inequality in economic wealth turns into inequality in social opportunities. Thirdly, public expenditure in education seems to be an effective instrument of equity: the coefficient of variable PUB is significant and negative, while the coefficient of variable PUB^2 is significant, but positive. Finally, an Educational Kuznets Curve emerges: namely, the coefficients of variable EDU and EDU^2 are significantly positive and negative, respectively. Therefore, the estimated coefficient on educational attainment and its square are consistent with Figure 3, which shows this evidence at regional level.

Table 3 Estimation Results for Italian Educational inequality

Dynamic panel-data estimation, one-step system GMM				
Variable	Coef.	Robust Standard Error	z	Pr> z
$I_{EDU_{it-1}}$.1952351	.0200524	9.74	0.000
$I_{PRIV_{it}}$	3.464.749	.4576152	7.57	0.000
$I_{PRIV_{it}}^2$.6083826	.0745037	8.17	0.000
PUB_{it}	-.1098643	.0104473	-10.52	0.000
PUB_{it}^2	.07556	.0345497	2.19	0.029
EDU_{it}	.1308076	.0668848	1.96	0.050
EDU_{it}^2	-.0321806	.0168	-1.92	0.055
δ_0	-1.702.543	.9837306	-17.31	0.000
year	.0103503	.0002806	36.89	0.000
Observations				1881
Test				
Wald chi2(8) = 4584.60		Prob > chi2 = 0.000		
AR(1)	z = -9.79	Pr > z = 0.000		
AR(2)	z = 0.95	Pr > z = 0.343		
Hansen test	chi2 = 171.00	Pr > chi2 = 0.127		

6. Policy implications and concluding remarks

In this paper, we developed an empirical analysis aiming at investigating the educational attainment and educational inequality in Italy between centre-northern and northern areas and across individuals in the period 1993-2012 by using a database constructed from ISTAT ADL survey. We applied the theoretical framework of Sen's capability approach, according to which public and private resources can be "converted" in individual or collective educational achievements such as years of schooling. This "conversion" can be represented by a function whose input variables are economic individuals' wealth and public expenditure in education, and "conversion" factors (namely, elements that influence the individual or the community conversion) are gender and territory. Through the econometric estimation of this conversion function, by implementing the Oaxaca-Blinder decomposition method, we found that the educational achievement process is strongly and positively determined by economic wealth and public resources: specifically, private resources are more significant but complementary. Moreover, we found out that educational achievements are relatively more difficult for females. The Educational Gap between the South and the Centre-North mainly depends on the relative ineffectiveness of public expenditure in the South of Italy, even if available sums are higher than those available in the Centre-North. Also lower level of economic wealth affects the gap, even if its effect is stronger in the South than in the Centre-North. The dynamic GMM panel model reports interesting results concerning individual inequality. This appears to be path dependent and strongly linked to economic inequality. Furthermore, public expenditure per capita in education is an effective instrument to promote educational equality. We also found the Kuznets inverted-U relationship between educational attainment and educational inequality.

This paper represents an original contribution to literature from various points of view. Firstly, we constructed a micro-data set by using the ADL survey for the period 1993-2012 and computed educational attainment at individual level and educational inequality measures at regional level. With the aim of analysing factors influencing educational attainment and to explore whether and to what extent educational levels relate to inequality, we applied the pseudo-panel framework which allowed us to take temporal dynamics into account. More specifically, this paper shows novel empirical evidence on the issue of monitoring Italian social progress in a long period, by building specific measures: an educational Gini index, an economic wealth index and a Gini Index of the economic wealth. Moreover, it proposes an original analysis of the educational Gap between the South and the Centre-North-by using the Oaxaca-Blinder method, which is generally used to analyse social group differences (such as sex, ethnic groups). Finally, the focus on territory as an important conversion factor is a rare investigation within the empirical studies on Sen's capability approach, and, at the same time, this element is coherent with Sen's framework where the individual is not a monad, but

interacts with others and the environment. The territorialisation of the capability approach is a new promising research field as illustrated by Biggeri and Ferrannini (2014).

Relevant political implications emerge from our econometric results. Institutions should strive to achieve a socially optimal combination of private and public educational drivers by sustaining the two main pillars of the school system: quality of provision and equality of access. The abovementioned public-private complementarity can reflect the complementarity between equity and efficiency in education, as estimated by Wößmann and Schütz (2006). Since, as underlined in many studies (see for example Singh, 2014), education equality is strongly linked to social, economic and gender equality. Moreover, education inequality can generate a multidimensional trap that risks to become permanent without sound public interventions to eliminate the roots of marginalisation (Bourguignon et al. 2007; World Bank, 2006; Marrero a Rodríguez, 2013; UNESCO, 2013). Then, the empirical results corroborate the importance of the European efforts for educational inclusion (Hippe et al., 2016). In synthesis, the main policy implications of the work are mainly two: to foster universal access to the school system which can break the worrying tie between economic inequality and educational inequality and to implement institutional mechanisms in order to evaluate the educational returns of public expenditure.

In conclusion, the results of this empirical study can have a positive effect on social policies, as pointed out in Checchi et al. (2016): they can provide more detailed information about inequality, which will make redistributive policies more acceptable for electors, and can stimulate further studies on educational inequality in specific social subgroups, which will urge more effective public interventions.

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